

Consistency of Angles and the Fine-Structure Constant

Kevin L. Davies

Hawaii Natural Energy Institute, University of Hawai'i at Mānoa, 1680 East West Road, POST 109, Honolulu, HI 96825

E-mail: kdavies@hawaii.edu

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Author is no longer affiliated with the University of Hawai'i. This work was originally developed in 2019 and is posted to Zenodo in light of recent experimental findings on quantized electron-phonon interactions and their connection to the fine-structure constant. Current correspondence: kdavies4@gmail.com

Abstract. The purpose of this work is to investigate how the assumption that angle is dimensionless has affected our expression and understanding of fundamental constants and equations in SI. The approach is to (i) define the radian and cycle as units of dimension angle related by $\text{cyc} = 2\pi \text{ rad}$ and (ii) attempt to reverse the implications and loss of information that have been introduced by previously setting $\text{rad} = 1$ and the unit hertz to s^{-1} rather than cyc/s . An important result is that the analysis indicates that the fine-structure is not dimensionless as universally accepted; rather it is an angle of approximately 0.4181° . Using the Bohr hydrogen model, this angle can be interpreted as the phase lag between the electric field seen at the center of the nucleus due to the electron and the field indicated by the electron's actual position. If the fine-structure constant is an angle as suggested, then it can be normalized to create new systems of natural units (with $\text{rad} \approx 137.04$). In this class of natural units, Coulomb's constant and the magnetic force constant are simple expressions of the von Klitzing constant and the speed of light, without the need for intermediate constants for the characteristic impedance of vacuum, vacuum permittivity, or vacuum permeability.

Keywords: SI, angle, radian, dimensionless, Planck constant, von Klitzing constant

1. Introduction

There is considerable discussion in the literature regarding the dimensionality and units of angle. The points of discussion include whether angle constitutes a dimension or not, the implications of normalizing the unit radian, if and how SI should be altered to explicitly handle angle as a dimension, and the types and units of frequency. This paper adds to this discussion by presenting, applying, and reviewing the implications of an approach to introduce angle and the units radian and cycle into existing equations, constants, and units where it has been previously removed by normalization.

The International Bureau of Weights and Measures (BIPM) states that plane angle is dimensionless because it is the ratio of arclength to radius—quantities of the same kind [1, 2]. This results in the unit radian (rad) having a value of m/m, making it a derived unit or simply unity [1, p. 137, 151]. However, Quincey, Mohr, and Phillips note that the SI units are based on a resolution that angle should be interpreted as dimensionless, which does not mean it is inherently dimensionless [1, 3]. Torrens and Emerson independently state that although angle can be measured as a ratio s/r of arclength s to radius r , this does not mean that angle *is* that ratio [4, 5]. Torrens suggests that the ratio is the angle expressed *in* radians—not the angle itself. Thus the angle is $s \text{ rad}/r$, where the radian is a unit of angle which may constitute a dimension. Stated otherwise, the interpretation of s/r as an angle ignores the aspect of curvature.

A contradiction occurs in SI when the $\text{rad} = 1$ assignment is considered alongside the definition of the unit hertz (Hz) as s^{-1} and the common understanding of Hz as cycles per second [1, 6, 7]. This would imply that the unit cycle, although not recognized in SI, would also be equal to one. However, this contradicts trigonometry which shows that one cycle is 2π radians. BIPM supported the common understanding of Hz in 2006 [8, p. 120], but since then backed away from the association between Hz and cycles per second by stating that although “cycle/s” is sometimes used in place of Hz, the cycle is not defined or recognized in SI [1, p. 140]. Thus we could continue to ignore the interlying problem, but BIPM also warns against possible errors by a factor of 2π [1]. The resolution is that s^{-1} should not be substituted for Hz or rad/s [1], even though these substitutions are valid by definition. Furthermore, types of frequency should be distinguished. Besides the clear distinction between angular or periodic frequencies and counting or stochastic frequencies (or rates) such as those using the unit becquerel, BIPM distinguishes between periodic frequency (or just “frequency”) and angular frequency (or angular velocity). Each of these implies

a different unit (Hz vs rad/s) which should be explicitly shown. However, since units are often factored into or otherwise associated with algebraic variables (such as f or ω), we must know which unit to use based on context and symbol convention alone. This seems to be a fragile approach, prone to the stated 2π errors.

Further confusion exists around the units for torque. In 2006 BIPM stated that torque may be interpreted as energy per angle (suggesting the unit J/rad), but dropped this language in 2019 [1, 8]. Regardless, BIPM is clear that the unit joule (J) should never be used for torque, even though it is mathematically equivalent to the recommended unit of newton-meter (Nm). We must remember to use angular velocity (or angular frequency but not frequency) as the power conjugate quantity, even though the units are mathematically equivalent, or else we will introduce an error of 2π . This is aggravated by the fact that the revolution (or cycle) is often a more convenient and comprehensible unit than the radian in physical applications.

There are a range of positions on how to address these apparently strong arguments for angle as a dimension. BIPM has clearly taken the position that angle should not be considered as a dimension and that we should rely on context and convention. Mohr proposes aggressive changes to SI, and he acknowledges that “[f]ixing the problem is not going to be easy, as evidenced by the fact that it has persisted for so many years after the institution of the SI in 1960” [6]. Quincy, Mohr, and Phillips together take a more moderate stance: “the diversity of viewpoints expressed in these and other works underscores the fact there is no single ‘correct’ way to treat angles, but rather the goal should be to provide a way that is most useful for the users of units” [3].

In this paper, we proceed with the basis that angle is a dimension of measurement, like length or mass. Instead of addressing what should be actually done with SI, we focus on reverse engineering how fundamental equations and constants would be expressed if angle was not normalized. We argue that this normalization has not only introduced the confusion and risk of errors discussed above, but it also has obfuscated our physical understanding of key constants. This very centrally and importantly involves the fine-structure constant, which predates SI.

2. Approach

For this analysis, we will augment the seven existing SI dimensions (time T, length L, mass M, electric current I, thermodynamic temperature Θ , amount of substance N, and luminous intensity J) with angle A. We consider that any frequency that is cyclic or

periodic in nature has a dimensionality of angle per time (regardless of whether it is stated as “angular” or “rotational”, as angular velocity, or has no qualifier at all). We do distinguish other non-cyclic or non-periodic counting or stochastic frequencies; these may be best described as rates rather than frequencies. We assign and track the angle dimension and associated units through a number of key constants and equations in quantum mechanics, electromagnetics, and the rotational mechanics. Throughout the paper, we introduce modified forms of key constants and units that incorporate angle; these are indicated with a prime symbol ($'$). The first time a constant is introduced, we show its dimensionality in square brackets on the right.

To begin, we use trigonometry to define the unit cycle (cyc) in terms of the unit radian as:

$$\text{cyc} = 2\pi \text{ rad} \quad [\text{A}] \quad (1)$$

Here, rad is not 1, and furthermore it is not a number. Next we use the unit cycle to define frequency f' with explicit angle:

$$f' = f \text{ cyc} \quad [\text{A T}^{-1}] \quad (2)$$

where f is the traditional frequency expressed as a product of a number and Hz. If angular frequency ω is instead expressed as a product of a number and unit 1/s (either directly or via BIPM’s rad = 1 assignment), then f' is also equal to ω rad through the traditional relation $\omega = 2\pi f$ and Eq. 1. We will always express f' as the product of a number and a unit of angle per time. This is typically rad/s or Hz', which is defined as follows:

$$\text{Hz}' = \text{cyc/s} = \text{Hz cyc} \quad [\text{AT}^{-1}] \quad (3)$$

In literature and common discourse in certain contexts (e.g. magnetic circuits and rotational mechanics), we also see the units turn, rotation, revolution, and degree ($^\circ$); these are also considered to be units of angle.

In the next section we use the preceding equations to introduce the dimension of angle into a number of key constants and well-known equations. This is challenging because we must reverse the ambiguity introduced by BIPM’s rad = 1 definition. Using that definition, we could in theory introduce any factor of angle into any existing constant definition or unit relation. When Hz appears in existing equations, we use Eq. 3 to replace it with Hz'. However, using the BIPM definition of Hz, we could also potentially replace any occurrences of the unit second with 1/Hz.

In general, we seek the simplest consistent and physically meaningful expression of key constants and equations. We use several principles to guide this process. The first is to begin with physical

constants that depend only on previously defined constants, preferably as few as possible. Second, we choose constants that are most directly associated with physical experiments, where the dimensionality tends to be clearer. Third, a unit of angle should not directly appear in a physical equation apart from describing a specific physical quantity; rather it should be incorporated into existing terms and factors. Finally, expressions should be simplified as much as reasonably possible, for instance by replacing factors of 2π by cyc/rad (according to Eq. 1) and incorporating those units into existing physical factors.

3. Application

3.1. Planck’s constant and quantum electromagnetics

The Planck-Einstein relation [9, p. 143] can be stated as follows:

$$E = h' f' \quad [\text{ML}^2 \text{T}^{-2}] \quad (4)$$

where $h' = h/\text{cyc} = \hbar/\text{rad}$ [$\text{ML}^2 \text{T}^{-1} \text{A}^{-1}$]. Fundamentally, Planck’s constant relates energy and frequency, and this form (h') allows (and requires) the frequency to be expressed with explicit angle. Note that Mohr [6] also promotes the use of explicit angle in Planck’s constant.

The Josephson constant can be correspondingly expressed with explicit angle as

$$K'_J = 2e/h' = K_J \text{ cyc} \quad [\text{T}^2 \text{I A M}^{-1} \text{L}^{-2}] \quad (5)$$

The value of K'_J can be determined by measuring the Josephson effect, which is fundamentally a relationship between frequency and voltage [1, p. 177]. Given K'_J , we can establish the unit Hz'/V using the following equation which is directly related to [1, p. 177]‡:

$$K'_J = 483\,597.9 \times 10^9 \text{ Hz}'/\text{V} \quad (6)$$

Similarly, the von Klitzing constant [10] can be expressed as

$$R'_K = h'/e^2 = R_K/\text{cyc} \quad [\text{ML}^2 \text{T}^{-3} \text{I}^{-2} \text{A}^{-1}] \quad (7)$$

The value of R'_K can be determined by measuring the quantum Hall effect. Given R'_K , we can establish the unit Ω/cyc using the following equation which is directly related to [1, p. 178]:

$$R'_K = 25\,812.807 \Omega/\text{cyc} \quad (8)$$

Thus far, with respect to defining the system of constants and units, we have five relevant equations

‡ We use the CIPM 1988 resolutions for standard definitions of K_J and R_K [1, p. 177], although abrogated by CGPM in 2018 [1, p. 197], because it best follows the guidelines outlined in Section 2.

(1, 5–8) and two relevant physical experiments that can be performed. Using these, the values of four constants (K'_J , R'_K , h' , and e) and three unit expressions (cyc/rad, Ω/cyc , and V/Hz') can be established. However, note that cyc (or rad) cannot be independently determined.

3.2. Electrical units

Given V/Hz' from the previous section and frequency from the well-established caesium standard [1, p. 127], we can establish the unit volt. However, we need a reference angle to establish the unit ohm from Ω/cyc and we do not wish to assume that $\text{rad} = 1$. Alternatively, we can establish a reference angle from a reference resistance. We choose the latter approach, and will later explain the relevance of the angle.

Using the Bohr hydrogen model, the von Klitzing constant can be interpreted as the ratio between the induced Hall electrical potential at the radius at the first electron orbit (relative to the potential at infinity) to the magnetic potential associated with its orbit:

$$R'_K = \frac{1}{4\pi \epsilon_0} \frac{e}{a_0} / f'_e e = \frac{1}{4\pi \epsilon_0 a_0 f'_e} \quad (9)$$

where R_{Bohr} is the orbital radius of the electron and f'_e [A T^{-1}] is its orbital frequency. Thus $f'_e e = I_e \text{cyc}$ [IA] is the magnetic potential or current times the unit cycle since the electric circuit involves one turn around the nucleus. We solve the previous equation for vacuum permittivity:

$$\epsilon_0 = \frac{1}{4\pi R'_K a_0 f'_e} \quad [\text{I}^2 \text{T}^4 \text{M}^{-1} \text{L}^{-3}] \quad (10)$$

This can be written in terms of the magnitude of the impedance of free space ($Z_0 = 1/\epsilon_0 c$) as follows:

$$\left(\frac{Z_0}{4\pi}\right) = R'_K \left(\frac{a_0 f'_e}{c}\right) \quad [\text{ML}^2 \text{T}^{-3} \text{I}^{-2}] \quad (11)$$

where the right hand side is the product of the von Klitzing constant and an angle ($a_0 f'_e/c$). This is the angle that an electron travels around hydrogen nucleus in the time that electromagnetic radiation can travel from the electron's position to the center of the nucleus. Equivalently, it is the angle that the electric field seen at the nucleus will lag the field indicated by the electron's instantaneous position, assuming the field propagates at the speed of light in vacuum.

Now, if we establish a value for this angle or Z_0 (or $\epsilon_0 = 1/Z_0 c$ or $\mu_0 = Z_0/c$, with c known), then we can determine the other. Either way, it will provide the information needed to establish the ohm and the ampere.

3.3. Fine-structure constant

One of the simplest traditional definitions of the fine-structure constant relates the magnitude of the impedance of free space to the von Klitzing constant [11]. It can be expressed in terms of R'_K as follows:

$$\alpha = \frac{Z_0}{2 R'_K \text{cyc}} \quad [1] \quad (12)$$

Substituting Eqs. 1 and 11, this is:

$$\alpha = \frac{a_0 f'_e}{c} / \text{rad} \quad (13)$$

We see that α is the angle from Eq. 11 divided by the radian. As suggested by our approach (Section 2), we incorporate the unit radian into a constant, and we choose the fine-structure constant itself by process of elimination. Therefore,

$$\alpha' = \frac{a_0 f'_e}{c} = \frac{Z_0}{4\pi R'_K} \quad [\text{A}] \quad (14)$$

where $\alpha' = \alpha \text{rad}$. Since α is known to be a dimensionless constant of approximately 0.007297 [12], α' is an angle with a value of approximately 0.4181° . However, since a physical value is the product of a number and a unit and we have explicitly included the unit angle in all of the preceding equations, we are free to choose a basis other than $\text{rad} = 1$. In particular, we can establish a natural unit system that sets $\alpha' = 1$; this just implies that $\text{rad} = \alpha'/\alpha \approx 137.04$. In fact, this may be more appropriate than $\text{rad} = 1$, which indicates a natural unit system where α' is not normalized but rather set equal to approximately 0.007297.

3.4. Coloumb's law and Ampère's force law

We now place the constants and units from the previous sections into the context of the macroscopic, classical experiments governed by Coloumb's law and Ampère's force law. We substitute Eq. 10 into Coulomb's law [8, 13]:

$$F = \frac{1}{4\pi\epsilon_0} \frac{Qq}{r^2} = R'_K \underbrace{\frac{r_e}{r} Q f'_e \frac{1}{r}}_{\text{electric field}} \overset{\text{magnetic potential}}{q} \quad [\text{MLT}^{-2}] \quad (15)$$

This can also be interpreted as the product of an electric field and a charge. The electric field is induced by a magnetic potential, which is a scaled version from the Bohr hydrogen model (according to $Q/r = e/a_0$). The von Klitzing constant converts this magnetic potential to an electric potential. The charge is simply the test charge q .

Likewise, we can substitute Eq. 11 and $Z_0 = \mu_0 c$ into Ampère's force law [13, p. 911]:

$$\frac{F}{L} = \frac{\mu_0}{2\pi} \frac{I_1 I_2}{r} = 2 \frac{R'_K \alpha'}{c} \frac{I_1 I_2}{r} \quad [\text{M T}^{-2}] \quad (16)$$

Equivalently, this is:

$$F = 2 \underbrace{R'_K I_1 \alpha'}_{\text{electric field}} \underbrace{\frac{1}{r} \frac{I_2 L}{c}}_{\text{charge}} \quad [\text{M L T}^{-2}] \quad (17)$$

This can be interpreted as twice the product of an electric field and a charge, where the electric field is induced by a magnetic potential. The “turns” of the magnetic potential is α' , which is the phase lag between the actual electric field and the field that would be produced by the instantaneous position of the electric charges associated with the current. The charge acted on by the electric field is the total mobile charge in the other conductor, assuming the charge propagates at the speed of light. The factor of two appears because the roles of the two conductors can be reversed with the same effect.

The previous equations imply the following values for Coulomb's constant and the magnetic force constant, in terms of fundamental constants:

$$k_e = R'_K a_0 f'_e = R'_K \alpha' c \quad [\text{M L}^3, \text{T}^{-4} \text{I}^2] \quad (18)$$

$$k_A = \frac{R'_K \alpha'}{c} \quad [\text{M L}, \text{T}^{-2} \text{I}^2] \quad (19)$$

If we use a natural unit systems where $\alpha' = 1$ according to the previous discussion, then

$$k_e = R'_K c \quad (20)$$

$$k_A = \frac{R'_K}{c} \quad (21)$$

Then Coulomb's law and Ampère's force law can be written in terms of the von Klitzing constant even more simply than with Z_0 (i.e. without a factor of $1/4\pi$):

$$F = R'_K c \frac{Q q}{r^2} \quad (22)$$

$$\frac{F}{L} = 2 \frac{R'_K}{c} \frac{I_1 I_2}{r} \quad (23)$$

3.5. Rotational mechanics

Torrens suggested that the confusion between the mathematically equivalent SI units of energy (J) and torque (N m) can be resolved by including angle in the denominator of torque [4]. The traditional definition of torque [13, p. 296] is:

$$\boldsymbol{\tau} = \mathbf{r} \times \mathbf{F} \quad [\text{M L}^2 \text{T}^{-2}] \quad (24)$$

No components of the right hand side (radius vector, cross product, and force vector) include a unit of angle. However, on a differential scale we can equate the work done by a force to the work done by a torque which does involve angle:

$$\partial E = F \partial l = \tau' \partial \theta \quad [\text{M L}^2 \text{T}^{-2}] \quad (25)$$

Therefore, the dimensionality of τ' must be energy per angle. Solving for torque, this is:

$$\tau' = \frac{\partial l}{\partial \theta} F = r' F \quad [\text{M L}^2 \text{T}^{-2} \text{A}^{-1}] \quad (26)$$

where $r' = r/\text{rad}$ is the arclength traveled per angle swept. Note that this is the inverse of the rad/r factor that appeared in the correct expression of angle in terms of arclength and radius (Section 1). Although Eq. 26 is scalar, it suggests that τ' is given by τ/rad and that \mathbf{r}' should be used instead of \mathbf{r} in the vector equation:

$$\boldsymbol{\tau}' = \mathbf{r}' \times \mathbf{F} \quad (27)$$

4. Conclusion

In this paper we proposed and demonstrated an approach to address challenges and concerns with angle and frequency in SI. We applied the approach to explicitly include angle in key physical units and constants including the Planck constant, von Klitzing constant, Josephson constant, fine-structure constant, Coulomb constant, and the magnetic force constant.

An advantage that was identified early in the paper is that when expressed with explicit angle, certain frequency-related variables can be consolidated. For example, Planck's constant (h) and the reduced Planck constant (\hbar) can be combined as h' , which is equal to h/cyc and \hbar/rad , where the unit of angle can be factored into other variables. Another example is that the traditional variables for frequency (f) and angular frequency (ω) can be combined as f' , which is equal to f/cyc and ω/rad . This reduces the need for different forms of the same underlying equation, and it prevents that potential errors of 2π that BIPM acknowledges [1, p. 140]. The unit of angle (rad, cyc, °, etc.) is factored out when the quantity is expressed as the product of a number and a unit at the beginning or end of a physical calculation; this directly handles any conversions that are required.

Another advantage is that the expression of angle avoids the potential confusion between energy and torque in SI [8]. Torque is expressed in units of energy per angle, rotational velocity is expressed as angle per time, and the product is power. To accommodate this, we suggested an adjustment to the traditional definition of torque as the cross product of radius and force.

The most significant conclusion from the investigation is that the fine-structure may not actually be dimensionless, if we consider angle as a dimension. The reasoning put forth in this paper suggests that it is an angle equal to approximately 0.4181° . This is significant because it could help solve the persistent riddle of a dimensionless constant that is not one and cannot be mathematically derived. This was stated by Richard Feynman as follows [14, p. 129]:

There is a most profound and beautiful question associated with the observed coupling constant, e —the amplitude for a real electron to emit or absorb a real photon. [...] Immediately you would like to know where this number for a coupling comes from: is it related to pi, or perhaps to the base of natural logarithms? Nobody knows. It's one of the *greatest* damn mysteries of physics: a *magic number* that comes to us with no understanding by man.

If the conclusion from this paper can be corroborated, then we can turn our attention from the persistent question of “Why is the fine-structure constant dimensionless?” to “What is the physical significance of the fine-structure constant as a quanta of angle, particularly 0.4181° ?”. We presented one interpretation as the angle by which the electric field seen at the center of the hydrogen nucleus lags the field indicated by the electron's actual position. This means that only a factor of $\cos 0.4181^\circ$ of the electric field is radial. The other 0.00266% of the magnitude of the Coulomb force must be provided by other means, possibly the magnetic field generated by the hydrogen proton's balancing rotation (180° out of phase with the electron and much smaller due to much larger mass). If so, the fine-structure constant may be related to the magnetic turns that couple the electronic current to the magnetic field produced by the proton's movement in addition to its own. This is generally consistent with existing knowledge of the fine-structure constant as an electromagnetic coupling constant [15] and more specifically as being “proportional to the ratio of the quanta of electric and magnetic force associated with the electron” [16]. There is much to investigate and discuss, but it is important to vet the ideas in this paper before going further.

The interpretation of the fine-structure constant as an angle is also significant because it establishes a fundamental constant of pure angle as opposed to mathematical units of angle such as the radian. This enables a new class of natural system of units where the fine-structure structure constant is equal to one (and the radian is not). We showed that with this assignment Coloumb's law and Ampère's force law can be simplified while also directly using a fundamental quantum constant, the von Klitzing constant, instead

of the characteristic impedance of vacuum, vacuum permittivity, or vacuum permeability.

In this manner, SI units and many other unit systems that explicitly or implicitly set $\text{rad} = 1$ can be seen as odd natural unit systems which normalize a mathematical unit rather than a physical constant [17]. One of the drawbacks of natural systems of units is that they allow key constants (and units in the case of $\text{rad} = 1$) to be removed from physical equations. This causes a loss of information and insight which can lead to confusion—the same confusion that is the subject of this paper. The first step is to re-introduce the radian and unit cycle where appropriate in the system of units and key equations; this paper suggests and begins to apply a method for that. The second step is to investigate other natural systems of units that normalize the fine-structure constant.

The proposed explicit treatment of angle requires adjustment to other constants that are less central to the SI unit system itself. These are outside the scope of this paper, but the modifications generally simplify the equations where the constants are defined and used, for instance by removing factors of 2π and eliminating the need for separate variables depending on context. A larger set of constants and units were previously considered by the author as a part of the open-source software packages QCalc and natu [18, 19].

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